

An Exploration the Challenges and Impacts during COVID-19 for Online Chinese Learning in Pakistan

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Abstract

Due to the pandemic COVID-19, schools, colleges and other institutes transformed into online teaching learning process. According to the official reports of Higher Education Commission (HEC) Pakistan, in august 2018 there was 7000 number of Pakistani students enrolled in various Chinese universities through scholarships offered by Chinese government. Hence, the number of enrollment increasing by new admission scholarship. Due to the significant number of enrollment there is extremely need to identify the challenges of Pakistani students faced during the learning of language course and their impacts on students learning progress. A mixed method research was attempt with triangular research design and purposive sampling technique used. The data was collected from Pakistani students those who were enrolled Chinese universities; it comprises 69 males and 28 females. A survey questionnaire and interview were conducted for data collection. The data was analyzed using SPSS software, the reliability and validity of data accomplished through chronbach alpha test.

1. Introduction

Since the global spread of the novel coronavirus, while international students in China still have the opportunity for offline Chinese language learning, Pakistani students who have returned to their home country can only engage with online Chinese language learning (Xia, Y., et al 2022). The blended teaching model of combining online and offline methods is likely to become a standard approach in the field of international Chinese education.

Conceptual shifts, technological preparations, and the current environment have also paved the way for post-pandemic international Chinese language education (Wu, C., 2022). In this new situation, every aspect of the teaching process, including instructional design, implementation, and feedback, requires continuous exploration and consideration by teachers. Teaching theories, practices, content, and methods must be re-positioned and innovated in response to the changing circumstances. Adjustments to teaching strategies are

urgently needed, and international Chinese education needs comprehensive enrichment and enhancement (Crok, C., & Gu, X., 2019). In the context of the

21st century, the enthusiasm for learning the Chinese language has been gradually increasing, and people from various countries who admire China have enthusiastically joined the wave of Chinese language learning (Zhao, H., & Huang, J., 2010). The education and research of Chinese as a second language have also become a more prominent topic of interest. With the development and widespread use of the Internet, its influence on international Chinese education is growing. Therefore, researchers are exploring how to leverage the Internet to transform the teaching model of international Chinese education, enhance the level of teaching, improve subject development, and promote the betterment of international Chinese education (Li, C., Zhang, L. J., & Jiang, G., 2021). In the field of Chinese language education, it is essential to summarize the patterns of online Chinese language teaching, develop online teaching resources, establish platforms for online Chinese language instruction, explore new teaching technologies, and integrate them with online teaching methods. By implementing a series of targeted measures, the post-pandemic era can witness facilitated sustainable development in international Chinese education (Piller, I., et al., 2020).

The main aims of this study to explore the challenges, issues and their impacts that

students have been affected. Followings are the research questions of the study that have been used for the interview conducting for data qualitative data collection process.

- i. What are the issues you faced during online classes?
- ii. What did you feel after absence of online class and you attend next lecture?
- iii. What do you feel after online Chinese language course? In terms of speaking or writing

2. Literature Review

The study was to contribute to the existing research landscape by focusing on the unique circumstances and challenges faced by Pakistani international students in their pursuit of online Chinese language education. Through a comprehensive investigation, it seeks to provide valuable insights into effective strategies and improvements for this specific group of learners in the post-pandemic era (Zhao Guoyan., 2021). Another study was attempt on Classroom Interaction in Online Teaching of International Chinese in the Post-Pandemic Era: Building on teaching practices and the data was collected through survey questionnaire which covered the insufficient classroom interaction in post-pandemic international Chinese education. The issue manifests in single-dimensional interaction methods, under-utilization of online teaching platforms, and limited initiative from participants in online Chinese teaching (Huang, L., 2020). Additionally, the study was focused on how Chinese English as Foreign Language (EFL) learners perceive and experience online and offline learning, shedding light on the advantages, challenges, and preferences associated with each mode of instruction. The study was conducted a comparative analysis of online and offline learning experiences, focusing on the perspectives of Chinese EFL learners (Yang, F., & Xu, M., 2020). Moreover, the study was conducted with the aims of to provide insights into how higher vocational education institutions adapted to the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic by implementing online teaching models and strategies, the data was conducted through survey questionnaires (Gu, J., & Chai, C. S., 2020). Besides, the study applied for the investigation of how the COVID-19 pandemic has influenced educational technology adoption and usage across various contexts. The findings of the study demonstrated changes into technology integration, instructional methods, and educational practices due to the pandemic (Ali, W., et al., 2020).

With the concerning of the online education during COVID-19, the study was recorded the discussion the educational implications of the COVID-19 pandemic and how educational institutions responded by transitioning to online learning. It mainly comprises the the challenges, opportunities, and adaptations involved in this transition (Ma Xiaqi., 2021).

3. Methodology

The study attempt based on the exploration and impacts of online Chinese course classes, applied the mixed-method research. There was purposive random sampling technique used for the data collection process. The open-ended questions were asked from respondents and self-developed questionnaires processed for data collection from Pakistani students studying in Chinese universities and attend the classes from home country due to Covid-19 pandemic.

3.1 Research Design

A triangular research design, also known as a triangulation design, is a research methodology that combines multiple methods or data sources to investigate a research question or problem. The goal of triangulation is to enhance the validity and reliability of research findings by cross-verifying or corroborating results from different sources or perspectives. This approach is particularly common in social sciences and qualitative research (Atkinson, D., 2016).

3.2 Instruments for Data Collection

There were two categories for data collection as instruments. One is survey questionnaires and other is open-ended questions. The survey questionnaire composed of 14 items, which are the reflection of the main objectives, and focused areas of the variables of the study with five point-likert scale. The open-ended interview questions were used for qualitative data collection.

3.3 Data Collection Procedure

Initially, based on the purposive sampling technique, the students were communicated through social media after that invited through email, and their personal contact number. The researcher was clarifying the aims and objectives of the study with research ethical consideration. After that the survey questionnaire and interview conducting procedures were applied for data collection. There are 69 number 71% male gender, and 28 females as 29% count. Though, total number of participants counted 97. Further details are illustrated in the figure 2.

Figure 1: Triangular Research Design

Figure 1 illustrates the triangular research design; it considers the most suitable for mixed-method Research. It has a parallel processing, after questionnaires development and open-ended interview conducting. Before data collection process, with the vision of research ethical consideration participants and interviewers were given briefly the research aims and objectives. The language, religion, culture, self-respect and time management were also the main consideration of the study. The quantitative and qualitative data were collected respectively. After that, quantitative data and qualitative data were analyzed and results were compare and contrast for interpretation the survey questionnaires and qualitative data.

Figure 2: Architecture of Data Processing
 Figure 2 demonstrates the architecture of the data processing, which involves data collection and it

considers a process of gathering information from all the relevant sources to find a solution to the researches problem. It helps to evaluate the outcome of the problem. Most of the organizations use data collection methods to make assumptions about future probabilities and trends. The data analysis is specifically used for decision-making. Primary data refers to the first-hand data gathered by the researcher himself or simply it is directly collected data by the researcher. It is a process of gathering data through surveys, interviews or experiments. The interviewer's data was encoded by unique code representations for further data organize procedures and the quantitative data also was organized, the Data organization is to arrange the raw data in an understandable order. It helps us to arrange the data in order to easily read and work. It includes classification, frequency distribution table, pictures representation etc. It will firstly be arranged in ascending or descending order. The organized for the data cleaning which covers the uniform of the data, for reading the data in a better way, uniform data follows a standard format, making it easier to analyze and compare. Data cleaning involve converting data into a common format or structure, ensuring that it is consistent and easy to work with eliminations of duplicate and null values for data analysis to generate the results.

Figure3. Conceptual Framework of the proposed study

Figure 3 represents the conceptual framework of the study, there are two categories variables; one is independent and other is dependent. The support strategies describes independent variable which covers the factors including, clear learning objectives, high quality learning materials, interactive learning environments, qualified instructors, assessment and feedback, language practice opportunities, student support services, flexible learning paths, motivation and engagement, peer support and collaboration , and continual improvement. However, there are three dependent variables (i) Learning achievement (ii) Enthusiasm for online learning (iii) Student's prior experience with online learning. Each variable is consisting of multiple factors; (i) Learning achievement: cover the factors knowledge acquisition, skill development, problem solving, language proficiency, academic achievement. (ii) Enthusiasm for online learning: it comprises the factors relevance and personal goals, clear objectives, recognition and certification, real world applications, learning community, adoptive learning, innovation and new technologies. (iii) Student's prior experience with online learning: This variable has the factors, previous online course, technical proficiency, Learning Management System (LMS) familiarity, self-

motivated and discipline, time management skills, digital literacy, online collaboration, cultural and

4. Results and Discussion

The presented study addressed the problem on the bases of covid-19 online courses by Pakistani students from home country to China, specifically; the aims were to explore the challenges that Pakistani students have face during online Chinese course. The nature of the research is mixed-method. There were two main components of the data generation one is quantitative data and qualitative data. The reliability and validity of the data is most important element which enables the researcher to effectively apply the tools and analysis techniques.

Table 1: Reliability Coefficient of All Variables

S.NO	Variable	Number of Items	Chronbach's Alpha
1	Support Strategies	3	0.824
2	Enthusiasm for Online Learning	4	0.835
3	Learning Achievements	3	0.824
4	Students' Prior Experience with Online Learning.	4	0.83

Table 1 shows the reliability of coefficient of all variables. For the variables and questionnaires reliability a chornbach's alpha test accomplished. There are four variables, support strategies consisting of 3 numbers of items with 0.824 chornbach alpha test. The enthusiasm for online learning comprises 4 items having 0.835 chornbach alpha test. Learning achievements based on 3 items with 0.824 chornbach alpha test. The student's prior experience with online learning has 4 items and 0.83 chornbach alpha test results were declared. For the validity of data a pilot testing was accomplished about 20 participant's data. After verification of data validation, further data collection processed with five point likert scale.

Table 2 Frequencies of all items

S-NO	Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Str Dis
1	You satisfied with the Duration of Chinese language learning for Chinese learners	11	49	15	14	
2	You feel proficient in Chinese language after completing the course	1	17	8	51	
3	You like to prefer online classes	3	21	11	57	
4	Online learning can help to improve your Chinese language proficiency	7	19	18	43	
5	All Chinese classes are online	29	20	6	30	
6	Internet access everytime for online classes	14	20	8	39	
7	You economically affected during online classes	12	57	13	11	
8	Online learning replace in-person classes	3	9	10	58	
9	The home environment affects online learning	27	52	11	5	
10	Timezone affects in your online classes	13	43	14	18	
11	Online learning create significant psychological stress	17	59	7	11	
12	You actively interact with the teacher during online classes	12	44	9	19	
13	Time duration for online classes is suitable	7	52	11	17	
14	You familiar with online platforms for classroom	13	17	7	46	

Table 2 shows the frequencies of the all items, there are 14 items . Each item has five point-likert sacle. Which are Strongly agree=1, Agree=2, Neutral=3,

linguistic factors.

Disagree=4, Strongly Disagree=5. For the item 1 strongly agree frequency is 11, and agree 49, these two numbers calculations shows that 60 number of participants are agreed with this statement. For the item 2, there are 51 disagree and 20 are strongly disagree, hence, this statement denotes 71 number of participants were disagree. For the item 3, there are 57 disagree and 5 are strongly disagree which represents the 62 number of participants are disagree with that statement. For the item 4, there are 43 strongly disagree and 10 disagree which shows that there are 53 number of participants are disagree with that statement. For the item 5, strongly agree 29, and agree 20, the calcaultion shows the 49 participants are agree with that statement. For the item 6, there are 39 disagree and 16 disagree which indicated the 55 are disagree with the statement. For the item 7, strongly agree 12, and 57 are agree that calculations represents the 69 agree. For the item 8, disagree 58 and disagree 17, the overall disagree for the statement is 75. For the item 9, strongly agree 27 and agree 52, and the total freqecny for the agree is 79. For the item 10, strongly agree 13 and agree 43, hence the obtained frequency for this statement is 56. For the item 11, strongly agree 17 and agree 59, though the calcaultion is 76 for the statement. For the item 12, strongly agree 12 and agree 44, the overall agree frequency is 56 for the statement. For the item 13, there are strongly 7 and agree 52, hence, the agree is 59. For the item 14, strongly disagree 14 and disagree 46, the satement disagree is 60.

Table 3: Quantitative data findings of the study

S-NO	Items	Respondents	Frequencies	StdDev	Mean
1	You satisfied with the Duration of Chinese language learning for Chinese learners	97	60%	16.772	19.4
2	You feel proficient in Chinese language after completing the course	97	18%	19.19114	24.9
3	You like to prefer online classes	97	24%	22.15401	22.8
4	Online learning can help to improve your Chinese language proficiency	97	26%	14.15274	16.5
5	All Chinese classes are online	97	49%	10.47855	17
6	Internet access everytime for online classes	97	34%	11.78134	20.6
7	You economically affected during online classes	97	69%	21.31431	19.3
8	Online learning replace in-person classes	97	12%	22.14272	20.2
9	The home environment affects online learning	97	79%	20.6228	16.5
10	Timezone affects in your online classes	97	56%	13.57571	19.1
11	Online learning create significant psychological stress	97	76%	22.73324	18.7
12	You actively interact with the teacher during online classes	97	56%	14.22322	20.1
13	Time duration for online classes is suitable	97	59%	18.58225	19.3
14	You familiar with online platforms for classroom	97	30%	15.30686	21.8

Table 3 describes that there are 14 items or observations. The item no. 1 shows the 97 respondents in which 60% Chinese learners are satisfied with the duration of Chinese language learning. Its StdDev is 16.772 and mean is 19.4. The item no. 2 shows that 97 respondents in which 18% feel proficient in Chinese after completing the course. Its StdDev is 19.19114 and mean is 24.9. The item no. 3 shows that 97 respondents in which 24% like to prefer online classes. Its StdDev is 22.15401 and mean is 22.8. The item no. 4 shows that 97 respondents in which 26% are satisfied with the statement that online learning can help to

improve your Chinese language proficiency. Its StdDev is 14.15274 and mean is 16.5. The item no. 5 shows that 97 respondents in which 49% are satisfied with all Chinese classes are online. Its StdDev is 10.47855 and mean is 17. The item no. 6 shows that 97 respondents in which 34% are satisfied with internet access everytime for online classes. Its StdDev is 11.78134 and mean is 20.6. The item no. 7 shows that 97 respondents in which 69% are satisfied with economically affected during online classes. Its StdDev is 21.31431 and mean is 19.3. The item no. 8 shows that 97 respondents in which 12% are satisfied with online learning replace in-person classes. Its StdDev is 22.14272 and mean is 20.2. The item no. 9 shows that 97 respondents in which 79% are satisfied with the home environment affect online learning. Its

4.1 Discussion for Qualitative Data Findings

The second main component of the study is interview conducting. The interview was conducted through online and phone call. Before initialize the process, all the interviewers were declared the research aims and objectives. The research ethics were also followed, furthermore, the permission was taken individually from interviewers. The open-ended questions were asked and answers were recorded into transcription format. The questions were translated into national and local languages of Pakistan for significantly understanding the main theme of questions. Moreover, the qualitative data was analyzed by Microsoft Excel.

4.2 Challenges and Impacts Faced by the Students

After the analysis of the qualitative data, the insights of the data shows, majority of students faced the challenges including Electricity and Load Shedding, internet, Limited Access to Technology i.e. students expectations to learn through latest technology but unfortunately unavailable to the access at home, Language Barriers such as a student who unable to capture the conceptual knowledge of the particular topic or subject, it considers the huge challenge for student to ask from a teacher or fellow students, Lack of Quiet Study Spaces, Communication Challenges, Assessment and Cheating, Limited Interactivity, Access to Quality Education, family issues, and mentally disturbance. Additionally, the students were lot of confusions if lecture is inter-related to the previous topic, lake of confidence, majority of students was feeling that the other students are more competent. It is also a challenge to response teacher and student feeling shy. The impacts consider that students not focused, irresponsible, not interested, just focusing to complete the time period. After completion of the course the students just learned alphabet in Chinese, some words for speaking in

StdDev is 20.6228 and mean is 16.5. The item no. 10 shows that 97 respondents in which 56% are satisfied with time-zone affects in the online classes. Its StdDev is 13.57571 and mean is 19.1. The item no. 11 shows that 97 respondents in which 76% are satisfied with online learning create significant psychological stress. Its StdDev is 22.73324 and mean is 18.7. The item no. 12 shows that 97 respondents in which 56% are satisfied with actively interact with the teacher in online classes. Its StdDev is 14.22322 and mean is 20.1. The item no. 13 shows that 97 respondents in which 59% are satisfied with time duration for online classes suitable. Its StdDev is 18.58225 and mean is 19.3. The item no. 14 shows that 97 respondents in which 30% are familiar with online platforms for classroom. Its StdDev is 15.30686 and mean is 21.8 Chinese, adoption the accent of Chinese, Not feeling proficient in speaking, listening, but writing somehow.

5. Conclusion

The study covers the mixed-method research approach, and addressed the problem for exploration the challenges and their impacts on online Chinese course classes during covid-19. A triangular research design has been used with purposive random sampling technique. There were 97 participants of the study 69 male and 28 female which considers the source of data collection. The survey questionnaires and interview questions were reflection of research tool of the study. The chronbach's alpha test was applied for data validation and reliability. The quantitative data analysis accomplished through Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software and the qualitative data analysis performed by Microsoft Excel. The study found the challenges and their impacts for learning process highlighted in the partition 4.2. the study is limited to the Pakistani students those who are enrolled in Chinese universities and attended the classes online from home country to China On the bases of exploration and findings of the research, it's strongly recommended to conduct offline classes for better productivity and produce the quality of education.

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